

Synthetic Approaches Towards the Benzo[a]quinolizidine System.

A Review

Aleksandar S. Pashev, Nikola T. Burdzhiev and Elena R. Stanoeva

"St. Kliment Ohridski" University of Sofia, Faculty of Chemistry and Pharmacy,
1, J. Bourchier Blvd., 1164 Sofia, Bulgaria

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Introduction

Recently benzo[a]quinolizidine ring system **1** (Figure 1) became of a great significance since it was found to be a key subunit in numerous natural and synthetic molecules possessing variety of physiological activities or being promising candidates for such activity.¹⁻¹⁰

Figure 1

The benzo[a]quinolizidine system **1** is found in the alkaloids of the *Schulzeines species* (schulzeines A-C (**2**)) and *Ipecac species* (emetine (**3**), tubulosine (**4**)). (Figure 2) The schulzeines **2**, isolated from the marine sponge *Penares schulzei*, are well studied and regarded as potential inhibitors of α -glucosidases which may be crucial for treatment of diabetes, cancer and viral infections.^{11,12} Emetine (**3**) was used in the traditional medicine, in the form of root extract from *Ipecac sp.*, for its antiparasitic and emetic activities. Later a more profound research was initiated on its ability to inhibit both ribosomal and mitochondrial protein synthesis and interfere with the DNA and RNA synthesis. In their article “*Biological activities of Emetine*”² Akinboye and Bakare showed the diverse biological properties of emetine (**3**) and some of its analogues, such as antiparasitic, antiviral, anticancer and contraceptive. Tubulosine (**4**) is indole-containing analogue of emetine and shows similar activities.^{13,14}

Figure 2

Despite the great medicinal value of **3**, its toxicity and side effects led to the search for new medicinally useful analogues. On *Figure 3* some of the latest synthetic compounds containing **1** are represented. According to a recent study,⁷ dehydroemetine (**5**), isocephaline (**6**), NZ71 (emunin), (**7**) and NZ72 (**8**) are promising anticancer therapeutics because of their inhibiting activity towards Hsp proteins and thus enhance sensibility of the cancer cells towards different drugs.⁷ All the compounds share the tricyclic system **1**, which seems to be essential for the activity. The benzo[a]quinolizinone derivative lirequinil (**9**) is a potential non-sedative drug which mimics the activity of benzodiazepines and may be effective for people with anxiety and sleep disorders.⁴ Tetrabenazine (**10**) is known to inhibit the uptake of serotonin, norepinephrine and dopamine in the CNS by binding to the vesicular monoamine transporter-2. Its chemistry and pharmacology is widely studied since it is used in medicine for diverse hyperkinetic movement disorders.^{8-10,15-17} Another interesting drug candidate, carmegliptin (**11**), is found to inhibit the enzyme dipeptidyl peptidase IV (DPP-IV), which is a new approach for the treatment of type 2 diabetes.^{5,18,19}

Figure 3

In the light of this broad spectrum of biological activity, many methods for the construction of benzo[a]quinolizidines are known hitherto. More than two dozen syntheses of emetine (**3**) have been described in the literature. Several include the closure of ring B by the Bischler-Napieralski reaction, by palladium-catalyzed cyclizations or ring C closure by the Dieckmann condensation, alkene metathesis or cycloadditions. There are few review articles on the methods for the synthesis of benzo[a]quinolizidines, e.g. by Saraf,²⁰ by Popp and Watts,²¹ and by Fujii²² followed by a short survey on the methods of synthesis of emetine (**3**) given by Montalban.¹ The methodology made a great progress towards the enantioselective approaches, which include the use of chiral auxiliaries and chiral catalysts at the very early stages of the multistep procedures, in order that the chiral intermediates could dictate the steric course of the reaction schemes till the end.

The present review will summarize the ring construction and the synthetic transformations of the benzo[a]quinolizidine ring system **1** within the frames of the notable total synthesis of alkaloids and potential drugs created after 1990 up to 2015. Older publications were also discussed in view of historical development of the problem, the improvement of older classic methods via the application of new reagents, or synthesis of some products of medicinal importance.

The synthetic methods leading to the ring system **1** are classified in two sections - **I. Formation of ring B**; and **II. Formation of ring C**. However, there are synthetic schemes that the successive formation of ring B and ring C is organized as a one-pot procedure, so the adopted classification is not strictly followed.

I. Formation of Ring B

1. Bischler–Napieralski Reaction

The Bischler-Napieralski synthesis is a Friedel-Crafts type acylation towards the synthesis of isoquinolines. The reaction is a cyclodehydration of 2-phenethylamides in the presence of a dehydrating agent, for example POCl_3 , PCl_5 etc. (Scheme 1).^{23,24}

Scheme 1

The synthesis of **1** using the Bischler-Napieralski reaction relies on the formation of C_{11a} – C_{11b} bond. The starting compound incorporates appropriately substituted piperidine derivative which upon cyclodehydration yields benzo[a]quinolizidine. Sugasawa and Itoh used the suitably substituted piperidinone **12**, which was treated by means of PCl_5 in pyridine to give the protected

benzo[a]quinolizidine **13** and further deprotected to give the 3-ethyl- benzo[a]quinolizidin-2-one **14** (*Scheme 2*).²⁵

(i): P_2O_5 , sea sand, pyridine, reflux, 6h, 73%; (ii): Pt/H_2 , EtOH, 10% HCl;
 (iii): 10% HCl, 1h, steam bath, 46% (over two steps).

Scheme 2

The Bischler–Napieralski reaction proceeds smoothly, which makes this methodology widely used in the natural product synthesis, e.g. 3-ethyl derivative **14** can be regarded as a key intermediate for the synthesis of emetine (**3**) (*Scheme 2*). The alkaloid **3** is probably the most frequently synthesized benzo[a]quinolizidine alkaloid.¹

The first total synthesis of emetine (**3**) was achieved by Battersby and Turner by means of Bischler–Napieralski cyclization.²⁶ In their procedure the starting piperidinone was converted to the ester **15** which had the necessary *trans* stereochemistry. Upon treatment with phosphorus oxychloride the ester gave the requisite benzo[a]quinolizidine derivative **16** in good yield. The product was isolated as a perchlorate salt due to its greater stability compared to the corresponding free base. Catalytic hydrogenation using the Adams catalyst produced the necessary saturated derivative **17** selectively and in good yield. It was used in the subsequent steps for the preparation of emetine (**3**) (*Scheme 3*).²⁶

Scheme 3

Ihara *et al.* used Bischler–Napieralski reaction in the formation of ring B for the purposes of the formal enantioselective synthesis of (-)-emetine (**3**).²⁷ The chiral lactone **18** was synthesized so that the configuration of the stereogenic centers C_2 and C_3 is the same as the one in the target molecules. Homoveratrylamine **19** was acylated by the lactone **18** to furnish quantitatively the amide **20**. Its treatment with POCl_3 allowed the simultaneous formation of rings B and C of the benzo[a]quinolizidinium salt **21** in one-step (Scheme 4).²⁷ The configuration of **18** dictated the steric course of the hydrogenation of the iminium bond of **21** which gave rise to **22** as a single diastereomer in 36 % overall yield. The latter product incorporated the benzo[a]quinolizidine core used as an important key intermediate for the synthesis of (-)-emetine (**3**) and tubulosine (**4**).²⁷

(i): 155-156 °C, 6h, 100%; (ii): POCl₃, reflux, 4h; (iii): LiClO₄, CH₂Cl₂/H₂O, 3h reflux, 1h, rt; (iv): H₂/PtO₂, EtOH, rt.

Scheme 4

2. Pomeranz–Fritsch Reaction

The acid-mediated cyclization of aminoacetals to yield isoquinolines is referred to as the Pomeranz–Fritsch reaction (*Scheme 5*). The reaction is carried out in acidic media, usually trifluoroacetic acid or boron trifluoride.^{28,29} The procedure works best when the aromatic ring carries electron donating substituents which leads to the formation of substituted isoquinolines.

Scheme 5

Rubiralta *et al.* were the first to develop an approach to the benzo[a]quinolizidine structure using formation of the C₇-C_{7a} bond by introducing the appropriately substituted *trans*-piperidine derivatives **23** in Pomeranz–Fritsch reaction.³⁰ The necessary compounds **24** were prepared by condensation of aminoacetals **25** with veratraldehyde **26**, followed by a diastereoselective Mannich-type cyclization. The *trans*-piperidines **23** were then converted to the aldehydes **27** which underwent acid catalyzed cyclization to the 7-hydroxybenzo[a]quinolizidines **28**. After reduction and acid hydrolysis the target compounds **29** were obtained (*Scheme 6*).³⁰

(i): C_6H_6 , 0 °C to reflux (Dean-Stark conditions), R=H (98%), R=Et (90%);
(ii): p-TsOH, C_6H_6 , reflux, N_2 atm, 1h, R=H (93%), R=Et (67%); (iii): 4N HCl, 0 °C, 4h, R=H (75%), R= Et (87%); (iv): Et_3SiH , TFA, CH_2Cl_2 , N_2 atm, reflux, 24 h, R=H (50%), R=Et (30%); (v): 4N HCl, MeOH, 40 °C, 7h, R=H (89%), R=Et (83%).

Scheme 6

Further development of the method was made by Hoornaert *et al.* that allowed the stereospecific synthesis of 1,3-substituted benzo[a]quinolizidines starting from the suitable oxazinone **30** which was converted to the pyridine derivative **31** with high regioselectivity.³¹ Reductive dehalogenation by treatment with hydrogen, Pd/C and PtO_2 resulted in conversion into the all-*cis* substituted piperidine **32**. Upon treatment with glycidol and subsequent periodate cleavage the amino aldehyde **33** was obtained. Cyclization of the latter with hydrochloric acid yielded stereospecifically the *trans*-fused benzo[a]quinolizidine product **34** which was then treated to remove the hydroxyl group. The *trans*-fused bicyclic system was proven by NMR analysis of the final product **35**.³¹ This method is applicable for the stereospecific synthesis of different 1,3-disubstituted derivatives (*Scheme 7*).

(i): H_2 , Pd/C, PtO_2 , K_2CO_3 , AcOH, rt; (ii): glycidol, $100\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$; (iii): NaIO_4 , $\text{CHCl}_3/\text{H}_2\text{O}$ -1:1, pH=8, $0\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ to rt, 3 h; (iv): 6N HCl, MeOH, rt, 18h, 72%; (v): H_2 , Pd/C, MeOH, HCl, 1 atm, rt; 89%.

Scheme 7

3. Pictet–Spengler Reaction

The Pictet–Spengler reaction is one of the classical methods for the synthesis of tetrahydroisoquinoline. The reaction is an acid-catalyzed condensation between a carbonyl compound and a β -arylethylamine derivative giving a tetrahydroisoquinoline ring (*Scheme 8*).^{28,29}

Scheme 8

The key intermediate in this reaction is the N-alkyliminium ion **36**, which undergoes an intramolecular cyclization upon which the product is formed. A modification of this reaction is the use of N-acyliminium ion **37** which is more electron-deficient and thus more reactive as an electrophile.³² Nucleophiles that are usually unreactive in the classical Pictet–Spengler reaction

such as unactivated arenes, participate readily in cyclizations with N-acyliminium electrophiles **37** (Scheme 9).

Scheme 9

As in the previously commented Bischler–Napieralski reaction, here ring B is closed again via the formation of C_{11a}-C_{11b} bond.³³⁻³⁵ One of the first reports featuring this type of reaction was made by Bithos *et al.* about the development of a new synthetic pathway to emetine (**3**).³⁶ Using amides of type **38** the hydroxylactam aldehyde **39** was synthesized which upon treatment with phosphoric acid underwent a Pictet-Spengler type cyclization. The tricyclic product **40** was used for the synthesis of emetine (**3**) (Scheme 10).³⁶

Scheme 10

Similar hydroxylactam derivative **41** was used by Bowen *et al.* in order to obtain the benzoquinolizidine skeleton **42** of the schulzeine alkaloids.³⁷ The key part in their synthetic approach was the chiral amide **43** with the same configuration of the chiral center as C₃ of the schulzeines **2**. The starting molecule for the preparation of **43** was the L-glutamate derivative **44**. The amide **43** is converted into the aldehyde **45**, which in acidic medium gave the hydroxylactam **41**, i.e. ring C formation preceded the ring B formation (*Scheme 11*).

(i): DMSO, (COCl)₂, NEt₃, CH₂Cl₂, -78 °C to rt, 2h, 79%; (ii): AcOH, CH₂Cl₂, rt, 2h, 76%; (iii): AcOH, CHCl₃, reflux, 72%.

Scheme 11

The cyclized product **42** was a diastereomeric mixture of *cis*- and *trans*-benzo[a]quinolizidinones.³⁷ *Cis* and *trans* diastereomers **46** were converted respectively into

(+)-schulzeine B and (-)-schulzeines A and C. The authors suggested an enantioselective total synthesis of the long chain aliphatic carboxylic acids, thus rendering total enantioselective syntheses of schulzeines A and C.

Lete *et al.* focused their attention on the transformations of imides employing two procedures - addition of organolithium reagents and reduction of imides.³⁸ Borohydride reduction of the glutarimide **47** followed by acid-mediated cyclization gave the benzo[a]quinolizidinone **48** in good yield. Treatment of **47** with methyllithium and subsequent acidic treatment afforded the 11b-methyl-substituted product **49** (Scheme 12).³⁸ The obtained compounds were further used in order to obtain the benzo[a]quinolizidine framework of emetine. Because of the availability of a wide array of substituted imides, the two approaches provide access to the heterocyclic framework of different isoquinoline alkaloids.³⁹⁻⁴²

(i): NaBH₄, EtOH/H₂O, HCl, 0 °C; (ii): TFA, CH₂Cl₂, rt, 83%; (iii): MeLi, -78 °C, THF;
 (iv): TFA, CH₂Cl₂, 87%.

Scheme 12

The potential application of these types of reactions in the synthesis of enantiopure alkaloids has been also studied. The products **48** and **49** were synthetically modified toward alkaloid-like structures. Lete *et al.* proposed a synthetic strategy which included a formation of an α,β -unsaturated lactam unit in the benzo[a]quinolizidinones **50**, **51** followed by a conjugate

addition reaction affording another functional group into the ring C.³⁸ The introduction of the double bond was performed in two steps – formation of selenium derivatives **48A** and **49A** and subsequent selenoxide elimination (*Scheme 13*).³⁸

(i): PhSeBr, LDA, THF, -78 °C, 1h (**48A**, 70%); (ii): PIDA, TFA, MeCN/H₂O, rt, (**50**, 56%); H₂O₂, pyridine, 0 °C to rt, (**51**, 61%, over two steps).

Scheme 13

The unsaturated products **50**, **51** were studied in conjugate addition reactions with sulfur-stabilized nucleophiles.³⁸ This allowed the stereocontrolled formation of a carbon-carbon bond at C₂ in the resulting product **52**. Deprotection with PIDA gave the aldehyde **53** as a single diastereomer, which was further used to obtain the emetine analogue **54** (*Scheme 14*).³⁸

Scheme 14

The reactions used in the asymmetric synthesis of natural products are based either on the use of chiral starting materials or chiral auxiliaries. Lete *et al.* showed that the cyclization of

hydroxylactam derivatives **55A** and **55B** could be catalyzed by chiral phosphoric acids, such as **56** and thus allowing the preparation of optically active products.⁴³ It was found that in the case of pyrrolidine hydroxylactams **55A** the reaction yields the corresponding pyrroloisoquinoline **57A** in good yield but with poor enantioselectivity (12% *ee*). The cyclization of the piperidine derivative **55B** was unsuccessful and only the enamine product **57B** was isolated (*Scheme 15*).⁴³

(i): MeLi, THF, -78 °C; (ii): 10 mol.% **56**, 24h, (**57A**, 64%, *ee* 12%).

Scheme 15

Another approach allowing stereospecific synthesis of benzo[a]quinolizidine molecules starts with the preparation of chiral substituted bicyclic lactams of type **58**. They are generated by cyclocondensation of racemic or prochiral oxoester derivatives **59** with (*S*)-dimethoxyphenylalaninol (**60**), which acts as a chiral inductor. Upon acidic treatment the final products **61** are assembled by an intramolecular Pictet–Spengler reaction (*Scheme 16*).⁴⁴⁻⁴⁶

(i): Toluene, reflux; (ii): TiCl_4 , CH_2Cl_2 , $-10\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$, 24h ($R^1=\text{H}$, $R^2=\text{CH}_2\text{COOEt}$, 68%); HCl/EtOH , $50\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$, 24h ($R^1=\text{Et}$, $R^2=\text{H}$, 80%).

Scheme 16

The condensation of the oxoester derivatives **59** with **60** proceeds with good yield and high stereoselectivity, and thus leads to the formation of an enantiopure products. The process involves a dynamic kinetic resolution of the racemic starting substrate **59**.⁴⁴ Under acidic conditions the oxazolidinone ring in **58** is cleaved leading to the formation of an α -acylaminium ion **58A** which undergoes a stereoselective Pictet-Spengler reaction. The reaction conditions were optimized using different acidic sources. Cyclizations initiated by $\text{BF}_3\cdot\text{Et}_2\text{O}$ or TiCl_4 lead to the formation of a single diastereomer **61**, whereas in the presence of HCl an isomerization of the C_1 stereocenter may occur. The cyclization leads to the formation of a product with a *trans*- $\text{H}_6/\text{H}_{11b}$ relative configuration which is guided by the hydroxymethyl substituent.⁴⁷

Franzén and Fisher suggested efficient one-pot enantioselective synthesis of benzo[a]quinolizidinone as a mixture of diastereomers **62** in 2:1 ratio in the presence of the basic chiral catalyst **63**.⁴⁸ In this method the formation of the rings B and C of benzo[a]quinolizidinone system proceeds in one pot. Yields varied from 53 to 71 % and the enantiomeric excess of the

11_b*S*-isomer of **62** was 90–98 % depending on the aryl substituent (*Scheme 17*). The configuration of the isomers **62** was established by means of X-ray analysis.⁴⁸

(i): 20 mol % **63**, CH₂Cl₂, 3 °C to rt, 1-5 days; (ii): HCl/Et₂O, -78 °C, 3h

a) Ar = C₆H₅, yield - 69%, *dr* - 62:38;

b) Ar = 2-NO₂C₆H₄, yield - 53%, *dr* - 83:17;

d) Ar = 4-MeOC₆H₄, yield - 71%, *dr* - 76:24;

e) Ar = 4-BrC₆H₄, yield - 56%, *dr* - 72:28.

Scheme 17

A possible mechanism for the reaction was also presented according to which the key stage of the reaction is a stereospecific conjugate addition of the starting amide **64** to the iminium ion, which resulted from initial reaction between the catalyst **63** and the conjugated aldehyde **65**. The stereospecificity was caused by the steric hindrance of the aryl groups present in the catalyst **63** (*Scheme 17*).⁴⁸ The resulting hydroxypiperidinone **66** incorporated the thermodynamically more stable *trans* configuration between the stereocenters at C₂ and C₃. Acid-catalyzed dehydration of **66** gave the acylaminium ion **67** which underwent an intramolecular Pictet-

Spengler reaction to the final products **62**. The procedure was further developed as a one-pot method for the preparation of indolo[2,3-a]quinolizidines⁴⁹⁻⁵¹ with application in the synthesis of natural products.⁵²

4. Intramolecular Heck Reaction

The reaction is a palladium-catalyzed coupling of haloarenes or haloalkenes with alkenes and is one of the most widely used methods in the organic synthesis of complex molecules.^{53,54} Its applications in the synthesis of heterocyclic compounds have been extensively reviewed.⁵⁵⁻⁵⁷

Using a three-step synthetic strategy which includes a final Heck reaction, Kirschbaum and Waldmann obtained functionalized benzo[a]quinolizidinones with good yield.^{58,59} The first two steps of the synthetic route aimed at the preparation of the enaminones of type **68** starting from the homoveratryl amine derivative **69** and its condensation with a series of aliphatic and aromatic aldehydes. Lewis acid-mediated condensation of the resulting Schiff bases **70** with electron-rich silyoxydienes **71** furnished the desired enaminones **68** (Scheme 18).^{58,59}

(i): $R^1\text{CHO}$, CH_2Cl_2 , MgSO_4 ; (ii): ZnCl_2/THF (for aromatic aldehydes); $\text{EtAlCl}_2/\text{CH}_2\text{Cl}_2$ (for aliphatic aldehydes).

a) $R^1 = \text{C}_6\text{H}_5$ ($R^2 = \text{H}$, 43%), ($R^2 = \text{Et}$, 45%); b) $R^1 = 4\text{-MeOC}_6\text{H}_4$ ($R^2 = \text{H}$, 66%), ($R^2 = \text{Et}$, 52%); c) $R^1 = 4\text{-NO}_2\text{C}_6\text{H}_4$ ($R^2 = \text{H}$, 20%), ($R^2 = \text{Et}$, 73%); d) $R^1 = i\text{-Pr}$ ($R^2 = \text{H}$, 65%), ($R^2 = \text{Et}$, 64%); e) $R^1 = n\text{-Pr}$ ($R^2 = \text{H}$, 43%); f) $R^1 = \text{H}$ ($R^2 = \text{H}$, 47%), ($R^2 = \text{Et}$, 27%).

Scheme 18

The Heck-type cyclization of enaminones **68** giving products **72**, **73** with an additional double bond in ring C is shown below. It was established that when the substituent R^2 is hydrogen, the products **72A**, **B** contain an endocyclic double bond and when R^2 is an ethyl group – **73A**, **B** with exocyclic double bond were formed. It was concluded that if the R^1 -substituent

and the base employed were sterically demanding (for example – aromatic substituent and EtN(*i*-Pr)₂) the formation of the isomeric product **72B** is low. The method is applicable for the formation of benzo[a]quinolizidines with additional substituents in ring C, by varying the structure of silyoxydienes **71**. In all cases *E*-**73** was formed in excess over the *Z*-isomer. Any attempts to achieve asymmetric induction by using chiral phosphine ligands, such as (*R*)-BINAP was unsuccessful (*Scheme 19*).^{58,59}

(i): Pd₂(dba)₃.CHCl₃, PPh₃, DMF, K₂CO₃, 100-120°C,

(ii): Pd₂(dba)₃.CHCl₃, NEt₄Cl, toluene, Δ

a) $R^1 = C_6H_5$ (**74A**, 87%), (**73A** + **73B**, 45%, *E/Z* = 3/1); b) $R^1 = 4\text{-MeOC}_6\text{H}_4$ (**72A**, 76%), (**73A** + **73B**, 53%, *E/Z* = 3/1); c) $R^1 = 4\text{-NO}_2\text{C}_6\text{H}_4$ (**72A**, 65%), (**73A** + **73B**, 41%, *E/Z* = 3/1); d) $R^1 = i\text{-Pr}$ (**72A**, 30%, **72B**, 60%), (**73A** + **73B**, 34%, *E/Z* = 20/1); e) $R^1 = n\text{-Pr}$ (**72A**, 26%, **72B**, 42%); f) $R^1 = H$ (**72A**, 33%), (**73A** + **73B**, 27%, *E/Z* = 20/1).

Scheme 19

Aiming to achieve enantiomerically enriched benzo[a]quinolizidines Kirschbaum *et al.* also performed the Heck reaction of chiral enamines **74**. This yielded the product **75** as a mixture of isomers. The major products had an exocyclic double bond and differed in configuration at C_{11b} (ratio – 3:4) (*Scheme 20*).^{58,59}

(i): Pd₂(dba)₃CHCl₃ (5 mol.%), P(o-tol)₃ (20 mol.%), K₂CO₃, Et₄NCl, toluene, reflux, 3h, 32%, ratio of isomers at C_{11b} 3:4; *E/Z* = 85/15.

Scheme 20

5. Photochemical Cyclization

Characteristic feature of conjugated hexatriene-containing polyenes is their electrocyclic reaction which has found application in the synthesis of alkaloids and natural products.

The potential of these reactions for the synthesis of benzo[a]quinolizidines can be illustrated with electrocyclic reaction of a stilbene-like pyridine analogue, where nitrogen is a part of enamide moiety.⁶⁰ The benzo[a]quinolizidin-4-ones **76** were prepared by irradiation of substituted pyridine derivatives **77** in acetonitrile or ethanol solution containing hydrochloric acid, O₂ and I₂. The irradiation of **77** under these reaction conditions leads to *trans*- to *cis* isomerization and the latter configuration is favorable for cyclization to **76** (Scheme 21).⁶⁰

(i): hv, O₂, I₂, CH₃CN, R = H (94 %), R = Ph (62 %);
 (ii): HCl, hv, CH₃CN, R = H (37 %), R = Ph (60 %);

Scheme 21

6. Parham Cyclization

The intramolecular reaction between an electrophilic site and an aryllithium generating fused carbo- or heterocyclic rings is referred to as the Parham reaction.⁶¹ The aryllithium is usually generated by metal-halogen exchange and the subsequent cyclization depends on the nature of the side-chain electrophile. When the electrophile is a carbonyl group the product is a cyclic alcohol, cyclization with a carboxyl group will yield a cyclic ketone. In the last case the reaction could be considered an anionic equivalent of the Friedel-Crafts reaction (*Scheme 22*).

Scheme 22

The reaction is very useful for the preparation of aryl or hetaryl fused carbo- or heterocycles, and has found applications in the synthesis of numerous natural products.^{62,63}

A good example of the usefulness of the Parham cyclization is the procedure by Lete *et al.* for the preparation of benzo[*a*]quinolizidine species, which involves aromatic lithiation-cyclization sequence of imides of type **78**. The products were hydroxylactam derivatives **79** which were further dehydrated to yield benzo[*a*]quinolizidinones containing cyclic enamide moiety **80** (*Scheme 23*).⁶⁴

- (i): *n*-BuLi, THF, -78 °C, 4h, (X = CH₂, 83 %), (X = O, 88 %);
 (ii): TFA, CH₂Cl₂ or CHCl₃

Scheme 23

The authors used similar synthetic strategy for the preparation of different types of isoquinoline-fused heterocycles.^{65,66} An enantioselective protocol for preparation of isoindolo[2,1-a]isoquinolines was also developed. The main characteristic of the sequence was the use of BINOL-derived Brønsted acids in the dehydrogenation of the initial product.⁶⁷

II. Formation of Ring C

1. Dieckmann Condensation

The formation of ring C by Dieckmann condensation is a classic approach to the benzo[a]quinolizidine ring system.^{1,20,21} It includes a step of appropriate diesters preparation, which then react in the Dieckmann condensation. Sodium hydride or ethoxide, or sodium itself as basic reagents in solvents as benzene or toluene are usually used. The regioselectivity can be a problem if both side chains contain active α -hydrogens, then the yield of the target molecule is lowered and tedious purification may be necessary.

This approach was used in the preparation of 3- or 1-alkylbenzo[a]quinolizidin-2-ones, which exhibit tranquilizing properties. Thus, 3-isobutylbenzo[a]quinolizidin-2-one under the name tetrabenazine (**10**) is introduced in the practice for treatment of hyperkinetic movement disorder (Huntington disease).^{8,68} Starting from tetrahydroisoquinolines like **81** the racemic 3-ethylbenzo[a]quinolizidine derivative **14** was obtained and was used as intermediate in the total syntheses of emetine (**3**) (Scheme 24).⁶⁹⁻⁷²

(i): EtONa, anhydrous toluene, reflux, 2h;
(ii): 2N HCl, reflux, 8h, 82%.

Scheme 24

There are different methods for construction of side chains with ester moieties in positions 1 and 2 of the isoquinoline ring as in **81**. Aza-Michael addition with esters of unsaturated acids is often used. Mizukami prepared tetrahydroisoquinoline **82**, which underwent Michael addition to the diester **83** that was cyclized in the presence of NaH/toluene to give ethyl ester of benzo[*a*]quinolizidin-2-one **84** as a sole isomer, in 55 % yield (Scheme 25).⁷⁰

(i): CH2=CHCOOEt, Triton B, 52%; (ii): NaH, toluene, 55%.

Scheme 25

Mizukami prepared also compound **85** and cyclized it to the ester **86**. The change of the regioselectivity, as compared to the synthesis of **84** was explained with steric reasons. The 3-methyl derivative **87** as a close analog to the alkaloid rotundine, was converted to a compound called “isorotundine” (Scheme 26).⁷⁰

(i): NaH, toluene, reflux, 7h, 67%
(ii): 10% HCl, reflux, 90%.

rotundine
Scheme 26

"Isorotundine"

Using a similar procedure, a series of 1-alkyl benzo[a]quinolizidinones **88** were prepared in order to obtain compounds for biological activity evaluation. The α -substituent of the 1-(ethoxycarbonylmethyl) group dictated the regioselectivity to compounds **89**, obtained in moderate yields (*Scheme 27*).⁷³

(i): NaH (2,5 mol excess), toluene, 120-125°C; (ii): 10% HCl.

R	yields, %	
	88	89
Me	85	43
Et	80	66
Pr	80	43

R	yields, %	
	88	89
Bu	83	46
<i>i</i> -Bu	76	45

Scheme 27

The Dieckmann condensation was included in the approach of Schnider *et al.* as a key step for the total synthesis of (\pm)-emetine (**3**).⁷² The authors started from the diester **90** and accomplished 15 steps in the synthesis of (\pm)-**3**. Other key points are the early selective reduction of the 1-oxo group in **91**, and the elongation of the side chain at C₂ into 2-(carboxymethyl) compound **92** using the Arndt–Eistert reaction. The acid **92** was transformed into two diastereomers **93**, each of which in turn gave (\pm)-emetine (**3**) and its diastereomer called (\pm)-isoemetine (*Scheme 28*).⁷²

Scheme 28

The Dieckmann condensation was applied in the synthesis of carmegliptin (**11**) first developed by Hoffmann-La Roche as a DPP-IV inhibitor in the therapy of type 2 diabetes.^{18,74} A specific substituent is the pyrrolidinone moiety at the C₃ bearing a fluoromethyl group which fits in a lipophilic pocket of the enzyme according to X-ray data.^{18,75} The approach consists of 21-step reaction scheme including 16-step linear synthesis. The C-ring was formed by the Dieckmann condensation, with low regioselectivity, and 40 % yield of the target product **84** (Scheme 29).^{18,75}

Scheme 29

2. Intramolecular Aminolysis

The intramolecular aminolysis is a suitable tool when the starting isoquinoline derivative incorporates a δ -aminoacid residue so that the reaction between NH and the carboxylic or ester group will lead to a six-membered ring.^{76,77}

The first total synthesis of schulzeines B and C was accomplished by Gurjar *et al.*, using intramolecular aminolysis as the key step to furnish the tricyclic benzo[a]quinolizidine core.⁷⁸ The appropriately substituted 3,4-dihydroisoquinoline **94** was made by a two-step reaction sequence starting from the amine **95** to yield its amide derivative **96** and subsequent Bischler-Napieralski cyclization. Reduction of the substituted derivative **94** with NaBH_3CN followed by treatment with aq. NaHCO_3 gave the diastereomeric benzo[a]quinolizidines **97-S** and **97-R** which were separated by column chromatography (Scheme 30).⁷⁸

(i): EDC, HOBT, CH_2Cl_2 0°C to rt, 15 h, 84%; (ii): POCl_3 , CHCl_3 , 70°C, 3h;
 (iii): NaBH_3CN , AcOH, CH_2Cl_2 , 0°C, 1h; (iv): aq. NaHCO_3 , rt, 3h, 65%.

Scheme 30

Another synthetic strategy using an intramolecular aminolysis involves an initial Corey-Link reaction of a substituted tetrahydroisoquinoline **98** to furnish an α -azido acid **99** which cyclizes readily to form benzo[a]quinolizidinone **100**.⁷⁹ The tetrahydroisoquinoline **98** itself was prepared by a Pictet–Spengler reaction with the amine **95** and the vinyl ether **101**. Reduction of the azido group of **100** and deprotection of the hydroxyl groups leads to the formation of tricyclic product **102** which was further used for the synthesis of schulzeine B (*Scheme 31*).⁷⁹

(i): AcOH, 100°C, 24h, 33% : 41% mixture of diastereomers; (ii): (Boc)₂O, CH₂Cl₂, 92%; (iii): NaOH, NaN₃, DME/H₂O (1:1); (iv): TFA, CH₂Cl₂, 0°C, (v): Et₃N, DPPA, DMF, 47%; (vi): H₂, Pd/C, MeOH, 99%.

Scheme 31

The key stage in the approach of Itoh *et al.* towards the synthesis of schulzeine A was also an intramolecular aminolysis of the ester group in **103** initiated by Boc-deprotection which gave mixture of the diastereomers **104-R** and **104-S** in very good yield and high enantiomeric excess.⁸⁰ The necessary **103** was prepared by a multistep synthetic route starting from optically active aldehyde **105**. The two diastereomers **104** were separated by means of column chromatography and **104-R** was converted into schulzeine A (*Scheme 32*).⁸⁰

(i): MeCN, 10 °C to rt, 2h, 93%; (ii): H₂, Rh(COD)₂BF₄ (10 mol.%), R-MONOPHOS (22 mol.%), CH₂Cl₂, rt, 2 days, 99%; (iii): TMSOTf; (iv): K₂CO₃, 18-crown-6.

Scheme 32

The procedure of Li and Yang also includes formation of ring C by aminolysis of ester group as a key step.⁸¹ The ester **106** was alkylated by means of ethyl 4-bromobutanoate to give **107** with very good yields along with the side product **108**. The reaction was carried out in inert atmosphere to lower the yield of **108**. A possible mechanism for the formation of both **107** and **108** is discussed (Scheme 33).⁸¹

(i): *t*-BuOK, DMF, -60 °C; (ii): ethyl 4-bromobutanoate, DMF, N₂ atm.;
 (107, 69%), (108, 5%).

Scheme 33

Shono *et al.* developed a coupling reaction between iminium salts such as **109** and bromocrotonates **110** promoted by Zn. Investigating the scope of the novel reaction the authors

prepared a series of benzyl-protected tetrahydroisoquinolinium salts **111** which upon deprotection cyclized to **112**.⁸² The products of type **112** were obtained in excellent yields and were further transformed to the ketones **113** which have previously been used in a number of methods towards the synthesis of emetine (*Scheme 34*). The same approach was successfully applied in the synthesis of indoloquinolizidines.⁸²

(i): Zn, CH₃CN, 0°C to rt, 5h; (ii): HCl_(gas), Et₂O; (iii): H₂, Pd/C, MeOH, 2 MPa; (iv): Et₃N, MeOH, reflux 30 min; (v): LiAlH₄, Et₂O, Soxlet extractor, N₂; (vi): 2N HCl, THF, reflux 2h.

- a) R¹ = H, R² = Me, (**111**, 98%), (**112**, 95%), (**113**, 97%);
 b) R¹ = Et, R² = Et, (**111**, 91%), (**112**, 82%), (**113**, 93%);
 c) R¹ = CH₂CO₂Et, R² = Et, (**111**, 85%), (**112**, 83%).

Scheme 34

3. Aza-annulation Reactions

Aza-annulation reactions of enamine substrates with molecules containing 1,3-biselectrophilic centers has proven to be a useful one-step method to construct five- or six-membered nitrogen heterocycles. The methodology has been utilized as a key step in the synthesis of various complex structures of this type. Despite its many variations the procedure

involves three fundamental reactions: enamine formation; conjugate addition to an α,β -unsaturated carboxylic acid derivative; acylation at nitrogen.⁸³

Two approaches are most often used – through an initial *N*-acylation or with formation of enamine prior to the important carbon-carbon bond formation. The enamines that result from the second approach are stable and usually isolable, or sometimes readily available. The reactions of enamines with various Michael acceptors have been extensively investigated as a convenient one-step route to six-membered nitrogen heterocycles (*Scheme 35*).⁸³

Scheme 35

Heterocyclic enamines are versatile building blocks for the synthesis of various bicyclic and tricyclic structures with a bridgehead nitrogen atom. These reactive N-heterocycles have received considerable attention because they include a push-pull fragment and readily react with different bis-electrophiles resulting in substituted quinolizidines and indolizidines.⁸⁴ “Push-pull” tetrahydroisoquinolines incorporating enamine fragment such as β -enaminonitriles and β -enaminoesters, are easily accessible and their reactions with electron-deficient alkenes (unsaturated acyl chlorides,⁸⁵ esters and dithioesters,⁸⁶ aldehydes (polyenals) and imines (azapolyenes),⁸⁴ electron-deficient allenes and their precursors or analogues⁸⁴, azlactones⁸⁷, etc.) afforded ring C of benzo[a]quinolizidinones and various derivatives thereof in good to high yields. Such cycloadditions, which can be regarded as [3+3] - cycloadditions, were called also “aza-annulation reactions”. On the other hand, the variation of the electron-withdrawing substituents at the enamine fragment allowed the introduction of substituents at ring C of the

benzo[a]quinolizidinones.^{83,84} It should be noted that the presence of double bond(s) in the molecule of the electrophilic partner gives rise to benzoquinolizines with one or two double bonds at ring C.⁸⁴

The aza-annulation reactions of 3,4-dihydroisoquinoline derivatives such as **114** for the preparation of benzo[a]quinolizidine derivatives have been well documented. Compound **114** is presumed to be in tautomeric equilibrium with its enamine form **114A** which is usually formed *in situ*. The reaction of **114** with crotonic anhydride gave the products **115** and **116** with apparent lack of regioselectivity.⁸⁸ Furthermore, the attempted conversion of **115** into **116** proved to be unsuccessful. Using the double activated Michael acceptor **117** a regioselective addition was achieved. The initially formed product **118** underwent spontaneous retro-Michael reaction forming the derivative **119** upon elimination of diethyl malonate.⁸⁹ *In situ* reduction of **118** with NaBH₄ proved to be useful in order to avoid the latter process (*Scheme 36*).

Scheme 36

The 3,4-dihydroisoquinoline **114** has found application in the synthesis of several natural products. Upon reaction with **120** the cyclized product **121**, which incorporates a lactam C-ring (i. e. acylated N atom) was obtained in one step and in a high yield.⁹⁰ The product was then transformed to the compound **122** identified as a key intermediate for the synthesis of (±)-emetine (**3**, 28%), (±)-tubulosine (**4**, 18%) and (±)-dihydroprotoemetine **123** (Scheme 37).

Scheme 37

Ninomiya *et al.* performed photochemically induced aza-annulation starting with the acylation of **114**, which was carried out by means of unsaturated acid chlorides chosen in a way to introduce specific substituents at ring C of the resulting benzo[a]quinolizinone **124**, suitable for the total synthesis of emetine (**3**).⁹¹ The irradiation of the acylated products gave rise to **124** which were transformed stereoselectively into **125**. The steric course of the transformations was established in order to prepare synthetic bioactive benzo[a]quinolizidines (*Scheme 38*).⁹¹

(i): **114**, benzene, Et₃N, 1h reflux; (ii): benzene, hv, 5h; (iii): multiple steps.

Scheme 38

The aza-annulation reaction of **114** with the unsymmetrical β -oxodithioesters **126** gave regioselectively the benzo[a]quinolizidin-4-thiones **127** in one step and in very good yields.^{92,93} The pattern of substitution of oxodithioesters **126** dictates the C₂ and C₃ substituents of the thiones **127**, so a tetracyclic structure could be obtained as well. It is interesting to note that ethyl acetoacetate, did not participate in the reaction with **114**. Further the thiolactams **127** were converted smoothly into lactams (*Scheme 39*).⁹⁴

Scheme 39

The aza-annulation reaction of tetrahydroisoquinolines of type **128**, which contain an acyl group at the enamine fragment, with bis-1,3-electrophiles proceeded smoothly to yield benzo[a]quinolizidin-4-ones **129-131** in very good yields and high regioselectivity.⁹⁵ Unexpectedly

the reaction of **128** ($X = \text{COPh}$) with malonyl chloride gave the tetracyclic product **131** in moderate yield. It is presumed that the initially formed benzo[*a*]quinolizidinone **132** underwent further addition of malonyl chloride (*Scheme 40*).⁹⁵

129 $X = \text{COMe}$ (74%), COPh (72%); **130** $X = \text{COMe}$ (81%), COPh (85%)

(i): 3-bromopropionyl chloride, Et_3N , THF, 0 °C to rt, reflux, 4 h;

(ii): itaconic anhydride, CH_3CN , reflux 6-7 h;

(iii): $\text{CH}_2(\text{COCl})_2$, Et_3N , THF, 0 °C to rt.

Scheme 40

The aza-annulation reaction of **128** with a mixture of formaldehyde and primary amines (Mannich type of electrophile) allowed the formation of 1-acylpyrimido[6,1-*a*]isoquinolin-4-ones **133** in very good yields under mild reaction conditions. The reaction of **128** with benzoyl isothiocyanate gave 4-phenylpyrimido[6,1-*a*]isoquinolin-2-thiones **134**. This aspect of the reactivity of the enaminones **128** is important, because pyrimido[6,1-*a*]isoquinolines were shown to be potent inhibitors of c-AMP phosphodiesterase and exhibit excellent antihypertensive activities (*Scheme 41*).^{95,96}

(i): CH_2O , R^1NH_2 , MeOH , rt, 4-6 h; (ii): PhCONCS , THF , reflux, 24h, 61-63%.

Scheme 41

The cyanoenamines **135** unlike the enaminones **128**, showed a varying reactivity towards different unsaturated acyl chlorides. Cinnamoyl chlorides gave rise to 2-oxo derivatives **136**, while the acryloyl chlorides – 4-oxo derivatives **137** (Scheme 42).⁹⁷

(i): $\text{La}(\text{OH})_3$, MeCN , rt, 55% ($\text{R}^1 = \text{Ph}$, $\text{R}^2 = \text{H}$);

(ii): pyridine, rt, 96h then Cs_2CO_3 , MeOH , reflux, 24 h, 90% ($\text{R}^1 = 4\text{-MeOC}_6\text{H}_4$, $\text{R}^2 = \text{H}$);

(iii): $\text{La}(\text{OH})_3$, MeCN , rt, 57-73% ($\text{R}^1, \text{R}^2 = \text{H}, \text{CH}_3$).

Scheme 42

Dihydroisoquinolinium mesylates of type **138** reacted with unsaturated aldehydes (polyenals) to give the intermediate conjugated polyenes which further underwent

electrocyclization to 4-styryl derivatives **139** in moderate yields. The method was successfully applied for the synthesis of indoloquinolizines as well (*Scheme 43*).⁹⁸

(i): CH_3COOH , 3-4h, rt; (ii): Et_3N , CH_3CN , 6-8h, reflux
($n=1,2$; $\text{R} = \text{H}, \text{NO}_2$, 49-62%).

Scheme 43

Conjugated aza-trienes and aza-tetraenes **140** reacted with formaldehyde and primary amines to give 2-styryl pyrimido[6,1-a]isoquinolines **141**. The authors proved that the reaction started with addition of the Mannich reagent to the nitrogen atom of the starting compounds **140** and the obtained adducts cyclized with the formation of the 6-membered pyrimidine ring (*Scheme 44*).⁹⁸

Scheme 44

Aza-annulation of tetrahydroisoquinoline enamines was used successfully for the preparation of lirequinil (**9**), as well as its analogs – the 7-oxothieno[2,3-a]quinolizine and 4-oxoindolo[2,3-a]quinolizine.^{4,99} The synthesis of **9** started with the preparation of 7-chloro-3,4-dihydroisoquinoline-1(2H)-thione (**142**), which was converted into the enamine ester **143**. The

aza-annulation reaction of **143** with the sodium 2-phenylacrylate (**144**) gave ring C of the target benzo[a]quinolizinone as the ethyl ester **145**, which after aminolysis was converted into **9** (*Scheme 45*).⁹⁹

i) CS₂, Et₃N, ClCO₂Et, CH₂Cl₂, 0 °C to rt, 1,5h then reflux 15 min; ii) AlCl₃ then 2M HCl (58%) or PPA (40%); iii) BrCH₂CO₂Et, Ph₃P, Et₃N, CH₃CN, reflux, 40-70h (78%); (iv): **144**, ClCO₂Et, THF, rt (81%); (v): DDQ, toluene, reflux (64%).

Scheme 45

In another preparation of **9** developed by Spurr,⁴ the oxazolidinedione **146** as a good electrophile, was easily cyclized to the oxazolo[2,3-a]isoquinoline-2,3-dione **147** in a high yield. After methanolysis of **147**, the resulting dihydroisoquinoline **148** reacted with ethyl 3-(dimethylamino)-2-phenylacrylate (**149**) to form ring C of the benzoquinolizinone system of **150**. Further transformations of **150** into the bromoderivative **151** allowed the introduction of the carboxylic group of the acid **152** which gave rise to the carboxamido group of **9**. The steps took place in very good to high yields and were convenient for larger scale production of **9** (*Scheme 46*).⁴

(i): FeCl_3 , rt, 16h (90%); (ii): MeOH, H_2SO_4 , 65°C , 24h (85%); (iii): **149**, AcOH, 95°C , 3h (75%); (iv): NBS, AcOH, 95°C , 1h (80%); (v): $\text{Pd}(\text{OAc})_2$, dppp, KHCO_3 , CO, DMSO, 95°C , 20h (90%).

Scheme 46

The acylated Meldrum acids and their analogs, which are known to give upon heating the reactive acyl ketenes species, form benzo[a]quinolizin-4-ones in cycloaddition reaction with the dihydroisoquinoline **114**.⁹² Pemberton *et al.*¹⁰⁰ investigated acylated Meldrum acids **153** in reaction with **114** under microwave irradiation (MWI) in acidic medium and obtained mixtures of benzo[a]quinolizin-4-ones **154** and [1,3]oxazino[2,3-a]isoquinolin-4-ones **156** (Scheme 47).¹⁰⁰

(i): **114**, MWI, dichloroethane then $\text{HCl}_{(\text{gas})}$ (R = Ph, Me) or TFA (R = cyclohexyl) $140\text{--}160^\circ\text{C}$ (R = Ph, 91 %).

Scheme 47

It was established that the acidic medium favored strongly the formation of the benzo[a]quinolizin-4-ones **154** while in the presence of Et_3N **156** were major products. In a neutral medium complex mixtures were obtained. Additionally, it was shown that compounds **156**, when heated under MWI in acidic medium, were converted although not completely, into **154**. It was suggested that oxazinones **156** were intermediate products of cycloaddition.¹⁰⁰

The disubstituted acylketene **157** derived from 1,3-dioxin-4-one **158** was used in reaction with **114** under similar reaction conditions – microwave irradiation followed by TFA addition at elevated temperature. In this way the alkylsubstituted benzo[a]quinolizine-4-one **159** was prepared in 69 % yield (*Scheme 48*). The procedure was applied also for the preparation of a series of indoloquinolizidinones.¹⁰⁰

Scheme 48

In a search for inhibitors of mitochondrial respiratory chain Moreno *et al.* reinvestigated the reaction of 1-substituted dihydroisoquinolines **160** and 6-substituted 1,3-dioxin-4-ones **161** - a source of acylketenes **162**.¹⁰¹ By variation of the reaction conditions the authors could direct the reaction towards either benzoquinolizine or oxazinoquinolizine product. When the reaction was carried out under neutral conditions only benzo[a]quinolizidinones **163** were obtained. In the presence of triethylamine, the oxazinones **164** were the sole products (*Scheme 49*).¹⁰¹ A stepwise mechanism for the reaction via common intermediate for both products was accepted.

The synthesized compounds were assayed *in vitro* against the NADH oxidase activity of beef-heart submitochondrial particles, as a model of mammalian respiratory chain. Most of the tested compounds inhibited the whole respiratory chain in micromolar concentrations. In general, compounds **164** displayed greater NADH oxidase inhibition than their respective analogs **163**. Because of the moderate toxicity compounds **163** and **164** could be regarded as potential antitumor agents.¹⁰¹

i): toluene, N_2 atm., MWI, reflux, 5 min; ii): Et_3N , toluene, N_2 atm., reflux, 5 min.

Scheme 49

Azlactones (2,5-disubstituted oxazol-4(5H)-ones) are another kind of bis-electrophiles, which react readily with 1-alkyl-3,4-dihydroisoquinolines to give benzo[a]quinolizin-4-ones. Azlactones are easily prepared by cyclodehydration of α -(N-acylamino)acids in the presence of an aldehyde.

Ruchirawat *et al.*⁸⁷ carried out the cyclocondensation reaction of enolizable dihydroisoquinolines **165** with azlactones **166** and obtained the benzo[a]quinolizinones **167** as mixtures of *trans* and *cis* isomers. Ring C of **167** acquired the substitution pattern of the starting azlactone **166** and the *trans/cis* ratio depended on the steric volume of the substituents. The authors assumed a stepwise mechanism with the formation of *N*-acylenamines as intermediates which undergo cyclization to benzo[a]quinolizin-4-ones **167** (Scheme 50).⁸⁷

Scheme 50

The reactions of **166** with dihydroisoquinolines which cannot give tautomeric enamines lead to the formation of imidazoloisoquinolin-3-ones.⁸⁷

Acylamino compounds *trans*- and *cis*-**167** containing *o*-bromophenyl substituent, were shown to give benzoindoloquinolizinones **168** on treatment with CuTC (copper(I) thiophene-2-carboxylate) under MWI. *Trans*-**167** was cyclized to **168** with much lower yield than the *cis* isomer. The formation of the side product **169** was also observed (*Scheme 51*).¹⁰²

cis-**167** (R=H) gave **168** (71%), **169** (14%);
 (i): Cu(TC), DMF, MWI, 150 °C, 0.5 h. (R=MeO) gave **168** (57%), **169** (16%).

Scheme 51

4. Other Cycloaddition Reactions

The cyclocondensation of enolizable mono- and bicyclic anhydrides with cyclic imines is useful one-step formation of compounds with annulated pyridinone cycle. The mechanism of the reaction is still under discussion.¹⁰³

Kametani *et al.*⁸⁸ reacted 1-methyl-3,4-dihydroisoquinoline (**114**) with glutaconic anhydride (**170**) to give in one step 11b-methylbenzo[a]quinolizin-4-one **171** in 56 % yield. The authors accepted that compound **171** was formed by a nucleophilic attack of the methylene carbon of **170** at C-1 of the dihydroisoquinoline **114** followed by cyclization and decarboxylation (*Scheme 52*).⁸⁸

Scheme 52

Stanoeva *et al.* carried out a reaction of 1-chloroisoquinoline (**172**) and **170** in refluxing toluene.¹⁰⁴ The cycloaddition took place with elimination of CO₂ and HCl and gave rise in one step to 4H-benzo[a]quinolizin-4-one (**173**) in 36 % yield (*Scheme 53*). Benzoquinolizone **173** showed fluorescence at room temperature in solution, with relatively high fluorescence quantum yield.¹⁰⁵

Scheme 53

Similar approach was successfully applied for the total syntheses of dibenzoquinolizine alkaloids (thalictricavine, thalictrifoline, berlambine, canadine, cavidine, corydaline, xylopinine in racemic and optically active form) from 3,4-dihydroisoquinolines and suitably substituted homophthalic anhydrides.¹⁰⁶

Two successive cycloaddition steps were employed in the synthesis of 3-ethylbenzoquinolizidin-2,6-dione **174** in an approach towards emetine. The reaction of benzaldoxime **175** with 2,3-bis(phenylsulfonyl)-1,3-butadiene gave rise to the adduct **176** in very good yield. Successive reductive N-O cleavage furnished the rings B and C of the benzo[a]quinolizidinedione **177** as a mixture of diastereomers. The introduction of ethyl group at position 3 was carried out with a moderate regioselectivity followed by desulfurization to give 3-ethylketone **174** (*Scheme 54*).¹⁰⁷

Scheme 54

The three-component reaction with the participation of isoquinoline, diethyl acetylenedicarboxylate and substituted butenone **178** gave rise to diethyl benzo[a]quinolizine-3,4-dicarboxylate (**179**) in 47 % yield (Scheme 55).¹⁰⁸ It is interesting to note that dimethyl acetylenedicarboxylate gave 1,3-oxazinoisoquinoline. It was suggested that the reaction included the formation of a dipolar intermediate and a conjugate addition to give benzo[a]quinolizine **179**, or a direct addition to the oxazine product. There was no suggestion, however, about the influence of the ester group on the structure of the reaction product.

Scheme 55

5. Via Multicomponent Reactions

Mannich reaction is very useful for the closure of ring C via the formation of the C₃-C₄ bond. Gilles and Meyers performed an enantioselective synthesis of (-)-emetine (**3**) from the cyclization of tetrahydroisoquinolinium salt **180**. The authors started from the 1-substituted tetrahydroisoquinoline **181** with the desired (*S*) configuration. The aminomethylation of the **181** in a version of Mannich reaction was conducted for the closure of ring C to 3-ethylbenzoquinolizidin-2-one **182** in a moderate *ee* (Scheme 56).¹⁰⁹

The chiral (*S*)-1-allyl tetrahydroisoquinoline **183** was prepared and the allyl substituent was catalytically transformed via alkene metathesis into the unsaturated ester **184**. The aza-Michael reaction of **184** with acrolein gave rise to the 1,2-disubstituted tetrahydroisoquinoline **185**. Ring closure was carried out stereo- and enantioselectively by a second Michael reaction to the aldehyde **186**, identified as a key intermediate towards (-)-emetine (**3**) (Scheme 57).¹¹⁰

i) Boc_2O , CH_2Cl_2 , rt, Ar atm., 96%; ii) ethyl acrylate, 2nd gen. Grubbs cat., CH_2Cl_2 , reflux, Ar atm., 88%; iii) TMSOTf, CH_2Cl_2 , rt, Ar atm., 91%; iv) acrolein, CH_2Cl_2 , rt, Ar atm., 84%; v) pyrrolidine, THF, Ar atm., 84%, over two steps.

Scheme 57

The aza-Michael reaction was used in combination with the Darzens reaction to give 2,3-epoxybenzoquinolizidine in high yield.¹¹¹

Tietze et al performed synthesis of 12 optically active diastereomers of emetine (**3**) using the principles of the combinatorial chemistry. (*S*)- and (*R*)- Tetrahydroisoquinolines **187** were prepared enantioselectively and further transformed to give the stereoisomers of emetine.¹¹² A representative synthetic scheme from (*S*)-**187** is given (*Scheme 58*). Starting sonicated domino reaction gave the lactone **188**. Subsequent methanolysis and Pd-catalyzed hydrogenation gave the methyl ester **189** as a mixture of 3 diastereomers, which were separated chromatographically.¹¹²

Scheme 58

6. Via Alkene Metathesis

Ring closing metathesis (RCM) is a well-established process allowing the synthesis of a wide variety of cyclic systems from acyclic dienes.¹¹³ The reaction works well for the formation of 5-7 membered rings and proved to be very concise approach to the benzo[a]quinolizidine ring system.

1,2-Dihydro- and 1,2,3,4-tetrahydroisoquinolines containing at positions 1 and 2 allylic and homoallylic groups were used as starting compounds for the ring closing metathesis leading to benzo[a]quinolizidines.¹¹⁴ The 1,2-diallyl isoquinoline derivatives of type **190** were prepared and treated with Grubbs' catalyst at room temperature. The yields of **191** were high, except for the cases of more basic starting compounds **190** (Scheme 59).¹¹⁴

Scheme 59

In the total enantioselective synthesis of schulzeines the asymmetric allylic amination of **192** is used for enantioselective B ring closure to 1-vinyl-3,4-dihydroisoquinolines **193**.¹¹⁵ The reaction is catalyzed by a Pd catalyst in the presence of a chiral ligand (diphosphonite- substituted biphenyl), to give either (*S*)- or (*R*)-**193** with very high enantiomeric excess. Each enantiomer **193** was hydrolyzed and the respective free base **194** was acylated to dienes **195**. Subsequent Grubbs' catalysts-mediated RCM was used for ring C formation. The resulting tricyclic diastereomers **196** were precursors for the synthesis of schulzeines A-C (*Scheme 60*).¹¹⁵

(i): Li, NH₃ (liq.), THF, *t*-BuOH, 6h, 98%; (ii): NCS, CH₂Cl₂, -10 °C to rt, 10h, 63%;
 (iii): H₂, 10% Pd/C, MeOH, rt, 13h, 89%; (iv): pyrrolidine, C₆H₆, reflux, 2h;
 (v): TsS(CH₂)₃STs, Et₃N, CH₃CN, reflux, 4h, then HCl, 65% (over two steps); (vi) KOH,
t-BuOH, THF, 60 °C, then HCl; (vii): CH₂N₂, Et₂O, 94% (over two steps); (viii): Ra-Ni,
 MeOH, 20h, reflux, 92%.

Scheme 61

8. Synthesis of 8-Azasteroids

The cyclocondensation of 3,4-dihydroisoquinolines **203** with various 2-acyl-1,3-cycloalkanediones was studied by Mikhal'chuk *et al.* and it has been shown that it gives 8-

azasteroid products **204** and **205**, which incorporate an annulated benzo[a]quinolizidine ring system. Depending on the structure of the starting cyclic 2-acylcycloalkanedione, different 8-azagonanediones were prepared (*Scheme 62*). The authors showed that ring D could not be smaller than 5-membered ring. The products possess both steroid and alkaloid isosteric fragments and are structurally similar to bioregulators of animal and plant origin. Compounds **204** (X = CH₂CH₂) showed immunomodulation activity.¹¹⁷⁻¹²⁰

(i): AcOH, reflux, 9h, 75,6-78,5%.

Scheme 62

9. Radical Cyclization

Ishibashi *et al.* investigated the radical cyclization of (*E*)- and (*Z*)-*N*-vinylarylacetamides **206** by means of Bu₃SnH, which gave the diastereomeric benzoquinolizidines (*2S*)- and (*2R*)-**207** under the action of different radical initiators.¹²¹ It was shown that (*Z*)-**206** reacted more readily under the different conditions used. Best yield and excellent diastereoselectivity in favor of (*S*)-**207** was obtained when Et₃B was used as an initiator at -78 °C. The authors suggested that tetrahydroisoquinoline **208** was intermediate product and in *Z*-configuration it could adopt a less hindered conformation during the formation of ring C with *S* configuration at C₂ (*Scheme 63*).

(i): Bu_3SnH , Et_3B , toluene, $-78\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$, 46 %, $S/R = 37/1$.

Scheme 63

Conclusion

There is a constant interest in the synthesis of benzo[a]quinolizidines over the years due to their occurrence in numerous alkaloids and drugs. The present review summarized the construction and transformations of the benzo[a]quinolizidine ring system as part of notable total synthesis of alkaloids and pharmaceutically active products created after 1990 up to the end of 2015. The use of the Bischler-Napieralski and Pictet-Spengler reactions, Dieckmann condensation, aza-annulations between dihydroisoquinolines and electron-deficient alkenes; ring-closing metathesis; aminolysis of carboxylic acid derivatives or other multicomponent reactions proved to be very fruitful. A growing number of synthetic approaches use chiral reagents to improve the stereochemical outcome. This review shows that any reaction can be useful in case that it leads to the goal.

The authors regret any omissions that may have occurred in this review.

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